

Day 1 breakout discussions

Day 1: Landscaping recommendations and discussion points for the breakout sessions

The breakout sessions on day 1 will be focussed on the general findings and recommendations of the Landscaping report (see the links in the [README](#) to the report and to the separate images of the current and future landscapes). In this document we summarise that report into findings that are applicable generally to all the stakeholders present at this workshop, and this will provide the input to the breakout discussions.

During the breakouts we will ask for your feedback on a set of questions about our findings and recommendations. We will use Miro boards for this. PLEASE DO NOT go to the boards before the workshop starts! The best place to start the Miro boards is [the landing board](#)

1. **Breakout 1.** [Direct Miro Board link](#)
 - a. Of the mentioned aspects that *do not work well* in the current landscape: which do you dis/agree with and why?
 - b. How would you suggest we could tackle these aspects?
 - c. *Which of these are/are not a priority* for your organisation to tackle, and why?
2. **Breakout 2.** [Direct Miro Board link](#)
 - a. Which are the *recommendations for a future landscape* that you think are the most/least important, and why?
 - b. What do you see as being *enablers and bottlenecks* to taking up these recommendations?
 - c. *Which of these are/are not a priority* for your organisation, and why?
3. **Breakout 3.** [Direct Miro Board link](#)
 - a. What do you think of the suggestions on the *roles and responsibilities*, and why?
 - b. What do you see as being *enablers and bottlenecks* to the responsible parties being able to take up their responsibilities? Those of you who already perform these roles, do you have any advice?
 - c. *Which of these are/are not a priority* for your organisation, and why?

On the basis of your feedback during these sessions, we will be making recommendations, to the EU's Horizon programme and to the DNA and biodiversity data community in general about what needs to be done and how it can be achieved, in a practical, sustainable and realistic way.

What works well

A summary of what works well the current landscape

First, a little bit of positive news 😊

Within the different (meta)data publishers in the ecosystem, and between (meta)data providing publishers, there is **quite a lot of sharing and co-use of standards** (DwC, MixS, ENVO) **and (meta)data** (OBIS and GBIF nodes and between themselves, NCBI and ENA, ENA and GBIF), and a fair amount of **taxonomic mapping** (NCBI and WORMs, CoL, etc).

There are **plenty of places where one can publish**

- protocols (protocols.io, OBPS)
- software (Zenodo-GitHub, via software journals, WorkflowHub).
- sampling metadata (BioSamples, BioProject).- INSDC(ENA,NCBI, DDBJ) use these
- sequence data (raw and increasingly ASVs/OTUs, to INSDC etc.)
- biodiversity derived from DNA (OBIS, GBIF etc)

Additionally, in the omics and biodiversity world, it is more and more expected by journals that data associated with an article are made available (published)

There are **plenty of well-used standards and/or conventions**

- fasta and fastq - are human and machine-readable (not always immediately machine-understandable however, as the organisation of the data therein can differ)
- asv/otu - ditto
- DwC-A - ditto
 - for biodiversity data, the national publishers that feed into OBIS/GBIF often provide excel templates that are based on DwC
- and most provide metadata also in at least XML (machine-readable)

There are plenty of metadata fields available to be filled with information, either in the metadata records or within (for DwC) the data, accommodating almost all necessary scopes (geographic, temporal, omics, bioinformatics, taxonomic, etc)

Standardisation of metadata for software is also readily available via templates (CodeMeta) is also easily available

Many providers of data and material (biobanks) **are moving to expose their metadata in more machine-oriented ways**, which will make those information accessible directly via the web (eventually), as well as standardising the information and making that globally understandable.

What does not work well

A summary of what does not work well in the current landscape

Metadata

1. **Completeness** of metadata (either within catalogue records or as recorded in the data) leaves much to be desired: either fields are not filled in or not enough are mandatory. *Results in lack of reusability and traceability/trustability of the data.*
2. **Accessibility** of information given in metadata leaves much to be desired: protocols, softwares, platforms, material, and other input to material or digital processing steps are often not given, or are given as strings rather than as DOI/URL to open access published endpoints. *Results in lack of reusability and trustability of the data.*
3. **Lack of machine-understandability** of metadata: requires URLs over PIDs or strings, requires exposure in web-standards such as RDF. *Results in barriers to automated and efficient (meta)data sharing between organisations.*

Publishing (documents and data)

4. **Open Access publication of protocols** and procedures undertaken to produce DNA/taxonomic inventories is not yet a globally standard practice. *Results in a lack of reusability and trustability of the data.*
5. **Publication of specialist data in generalist repositories or just in scientific articles** is still quite common. Because these will not have specialist metadata fields, *results in a lack of Findability*, because they will not enforce data standards, *results in a lack of Interoperability*, and if they are not open access journals, *results in lack of findability, accessibility and reusability*
6. **Biomonitoring data** are too often published in limited-access local/agency repositories, which are generally more poor in their FAIRness.
7. It is not common practice to publish **intermediate results of bioinformatics**. Not everyone can reprocess data but will want to inspect intermediate results. *Results in a lack of reusability and traceability/trustability of the data*
8. It is good that DNA-based occurrences are published in biodiversity databases. But where those are combined with more traditional biodiversity data, one should ask: **do the users of these data fully understand the ins and outs of occurrences derived from omics? Whose responsibility would it be to teach them?**

Standards (data and metadata)

9. **Lack of guidance and consistency** over the full ecosystem as to which **standards** to use in metadata/data (e.g. vocabularies), and how and where to use them. More

frequent mapping between vocabularies should be done and should be easier to find. *Results in confusion and fatigue of the data creators.*

10. **Bioinformatics outputs** use the same formats but the information therein are standardised in different ways (e.g. how taxonomic classifications are written): full explanation of outputs often lacking. *Results in a lack of interoperability and hence reusability of the data.*
11. **Taxonomic identifications** in reference libraries and bioinformatics outputs can still lack URIs (i.e. a direct link to the name in the database). *Results in lack of reusability and trustability.*
12. **ASVs and OTU** are often not published *as data in their own right*: portals that do provide for this should be more widely used. *Results in a lack of findability of the data*
13. **Insufficient mapping between taxonomic backbones/systems**, within those which are omics-focussed and between omics- and classical-focussed. More mapping, more regular mapping, and more information about how mapping is done, is desired. *Results in lack of reusability of results, and fatigue on behalf of data creators when trying to make their results more widely findable and usable.*

Provenance and ABS

14. Is generally extremely poorly provided, by *everyone* in the ecosystem. *Results in a lack of reusability and traceability/trustability of the data*
15. Lack of consistent approaches to ABS (Nagoya Protocol) and any future permutations thereof. *This could affect all stages of DNA work, so should be dealt with at a DNA-community level.*

Tools

Tools, templates, guidelines to help scientists do the following:

16. find and use vocabularies
17. create interoperable spreadsheets
18. format bioinformatics outputs into DwC
19. publish large data files
20. describe provenance as metadata
21. describe software as metadata

Such tools, templates, and guidelines are not lacking – there are very good examples out there – but taken on a global data ecosystem level, they are

22. often fixed to a single data publisher, and so not (understood to be) generally useable
23. hard to find (e.g. via an internet search)
24. not strongly enforced to be used anyway (so why bother?)
25. not provided as a full system (i.e. a lot of manual work is necessary, e.g. a template over a tool)

Recommendations

Recommendations to achieve a better, future landscape

The current digital aquatic eDNA data landscape overall *has* the needed infrastructure. However, though the resources exist, there is work needed regarding data/metadata linking and enhancing accessibility and interoperability between infrastructures, and also improving usage/data submission to the right resources following community guidelines and internationally accepted standards.

A summary of the recommendations of the Landscaping report:

Provide more guidance to data creators on where and how to submit their data. Bearing in mind that they may need to submit several different datasets to different publishers, and may also have software to add to that, make this guidance cover all the stages of the process (from sample to taxonomic lists) and make this guidance highly Findable. *Results in more submitted data, reduces confusion and frustration for the data creators.*

Focus on machine-readable and -understandable web standards and specification for publishing and sharing (meta)data. *Benefit from the input from a wider community, allowing uptake by all sorts of other parties, and providing greater automation in sharing of (meta)data.*

Provide more tools for scientists to use to format biodiversity and bioinformatics data so that they are more interoperable at the level of the data file and of the *content* of the data files. *Results in more submitted data, less work for the data publishers to accept those data, and reduces frustration for the data creators.*

Encourage publishing pathways from local/thematic/national to regional/global. *Results in a widening of the net capturing scientific data, encourages collaboration between parties, improves funding opportunities.*

Increase the number of, and frequency of, mappings between vocabularies and between taxonomic backbones. *Improves interoperability and reusability of data.*

Reference libraries: connect them to each other as a decentralised network, communicating directly with each other and exchanging data. Not one large taxonomically-curated eDNA reference database of aquatic organisms of Europe (not feasible, necessary or desirable) but a diverse portfolio of independent databases. *Improves reusability of data.*

Samples: provide stricter and richer provenance metadata templates/fields. *Improves reusability of data.*

Discourage publishing specialist data in generalist repositories. Investigate why scientists do this? What can we do to help them overcome whatever their barriers are?
Results in more submitted data.

Work together to build the (meta)data standards, templates, and specifications for our community. *Allows for smoother interoperability between parties (between publishers), reduces confusion and frustration for the data creators.*

Work together to identify favoured vocabularies and taxonomies, specify how they should be used in (meta)data. *Improves interoperability and reusability of data, reduces confusion and frustration for the data creators.*

Push our funders (funding agencies, universities) to acknowledge data as much as science publications. Push the funders and journals to require data submission, or at least metadata submission, for all data created during research. Ditto for protocols, software, etc, Ditto for samples and data arising immediately from samples. *Results in more submitted, reusable data.*

Push our funders into providing for the resources to allow sustainable practices that can adapt as the future comes. Point out that without these stakeholders – publishers, reference libraries, taxonomic backbones, developers, DNA science would almost stop. *Results in the resources being available for this work to be done.*

Roles and responsibilities

Roles and responsibilities for and in the future landscape

The agents we will mention here are:

- Publishers: here we include those who publish data or metadata on DNA and biodiversity, and also biobanks that hold samples and their metadata
- Information providers: here we include those that create information rather than just raw data, being bioinformatics, reference libraries, taxonomic backbones
- Funders: here we include the national and regional (e.g. Horizon) funding agencies, universities, monitoring agencies
- Journals: scientific journals
- RIs: Research Institutions and in particular in Europe, the ERICs (European Research Infrastructure Consortium)
- Individual scientists
- The community: a nebulous word meaning all or certain elements of us working together

Metadata and data

Publishers

- Require more mandatory and richer metadata
- Require machine-understandable ways for those metadata to be provided (e.g. URL over string)
- Provide interoperable templates for data submission
- ...and enforce their uptake
- Provide machine-understandable ways for metadata and data to be exposed, accessed
- Always provide downloadable metadata with every data file / data set
- Always provide separate provenance metadata with every data file / data set

Publishers, RIs, and the community

- Work together to adopt common data standards / templates for similar data
- Work together to adopt common metadata standards
- Work together to adopt common vocabularies
- ...and to regularly map between vocabularies
- Create templates for provenance metadata (separate from the data and from the catalogue metadata)

Journals, publishers, RIs, funders, the community

- Require data are published before a project can be signed off or a science article accepted

- Encourage an expectation of Open Access publishing: always for metadata, always for publications, always for data (unless sensitive or IP)
- Automate the “embargo” period release: data under embargo should be automatically released once the science is published
- Automate citation tracking between journals and data publishers

Enforcing the use of metadata and data standards

Publishers are the only ones who can immediately enforce standardised metadata and data
Scientists and information creators are responsible for providing the standardised data and metadata.

However, funders are responsible for providing the scientists the environment in which this is encouraged; tools, time, training, and funding to do it

Rewarding the publishing of data

Ultimately, this rests on the funders: they need to acknowledge the publishing of data as strongly as they acknowledge the publishing of science papers

Creating tools and providing training

A very common comment from data creators – those collecting the data and creating the results – is that they don’t know “how to do it” or “why to do it”

- how to make their data interoperable enough to be easy to format into whatever required template a data publisher has
- how to use vocabularies, or even find terms in one
- why they have to fill in so many metadata fields, especially when that is all in the data anyway
- why should I take so much time to publish data when it is in my science article anyway
- why they don’t get acknowledged for publishing data as much as for publishing science

Who should provide the tools and training?

Clearly funders – especially universities and labs training and employing scientists

What about RIs?

Can publishers join efforts in providing tools and training?